

A CONTINUOUS ADJOINT METHOD FOR THE SHAPE OPTIMIZATION OF TURBULENT CAVITATING FLOWS

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Abstract

The onset of cavitation in hydraulic devices is caused by rapid pressure variations leading to the formation and collapse of vapor bubbles which can occasionally provoke severe damage. Shape optimizations for cavitation reduction, based on single-phase flow models, prevent static pressure from dropping below the vaporization pressure, but they do not account for the influence of vapor in the flow. In this article, a continuous adjoint-based optimization method for two-phase turbulent cavitating flows, using the Volume of Fluid method, is developed within an in-house GPU-enabled CFD solver. The adjoint accommodates new terms arising from the differentiation of the source terms modeling cavitation, the liquid-vapor mixture properties, as well as the turbulence model. The sensitivity derivatives are expressed in terms of surface integrals, using an adjoint formulation which, prior to this work, has been applied only to single-phase flows. The comparison of

the sensitivity derivatives computed by the continuous adjoint method and finite differences shows that the differentiation of the turbulence model equations, frequently omitted in two-phase flows, is necessary to predict accurate gradients. After the validation of both the primal and adjoint solvers, gradient-based constrained shape optimizations are performed in three cavitation-dominated flows around a 2D isolated hydrofoil and a 3D hemispherical head body, as well as inside a 2D hydraulic poppet valve.

Keywords: Shape Optimization, Continuous adjoint method, CFD, Two-phase flows, Cavitation, Turbulence model differentiation

1 Introduction

In gradient-based shape optimization (ShpO), the adjoint method, either discrete or continuous, is the most efficient way to compute the sensitivities of the quantities of interest with respect to (w.r.t) the design variables (Sensitivity Derivatives, SDs), with a computational cost that is independent of their number. The adjoint methods are widely used for single-phase compressible or incompressible flows, [1–3]. In this article, a continuous adjoint method for two-phase turbulent cavitating flows is developed and an in-house software is extended accordingly and used for ShpO cases.

Cavitation refers to the formation of vapor bubbles in a liquid flow when the local static pressure drops below the vaporization pressure. It appears in hydraulic devices featuring low pressure regions during operation. Cavitation must be definitely considered during the design, as it may cause material erosion, noise and vibrations, impacting both performance and longevity. Due to its complex behavior, trial-and-error design by interpreting numerical or experimental results is not straightforward, as the effects of manual shape modifications are often unpredictable. Consequently, automatic ShpO methods are essential.

Optimization algorithms require the prediction of cavitation through CFD solvers, which can be based on either an inhomogeneous or a homogeneous approach. The former considers different sets of equations for the liquid and vapor phase, while the latter treats both of them as a single mixture, sharing common velocity and pressure

fields and, thus, governed by one set of Mean-Flow (MF) equations. The homogeneous methods may compute the mixture density by means of a barotropic equation of state [4], but a more accurate alternative, adopted in this article, is to express it in terms of the volume fraction, defined as the percentage volume of one phase in each computational cell. The volume fraction field determines the mixture properties and is governed by the Volume of Fluid (VoF) equation, including source terms accounting for phase change [5, 6]. Another possible approach for simulating cavitating flows is the hybrid Euler-Lagrange method [7, 8], which solves the VoF equation in a Eulerian framework to predict large-scale vapor cavities, and resolves the behavior of micro-scale vapor bubbles in a Lagrange framework. This method enables the simulation of vapor bubble motion and size oscillations, both of which play a critical role in cavitation-induced erosion.

In the literature, both gradient-free and gradient-based methods have been used to optimize cavitating flows relying on single-phase simulations; these predict cavitation by checking if the local pressure falls below the vaporization pressure. [9] presents a genetic algorithm-based ShpO of a hydrofoil to minimize cavitation and maximize lift-over-drag ratio, with a constraint on the maximum thickness; in [10], the continuous adjoint method for single-phase flows was used to minimize cavitation in a Francis hydraulic turbine. However, resorting to single-phase simulations poses the risk of residual cavitation if the pressure is not raised above the vaporization pressure in the entire domain.

The literature of gradient-based optimization using two-phase flow models is restricted. For instance, [11] maximized the lift-over-drag ratio of a hydrofoil under cavitation by also keeping lift above the reference value. This was achieved by building a Response Surface Model based on two-phase results acquired from simulations around various geometries to provide a fast estimation of the objective as a function of the design variables. [12] developed the discrete adjoint for inviscid and laminar cavitating flows, modeled by a barotropic homogeneous approach; this was used to optimize a hydrofoil for maximum lift, cavitation suppression and to reproduce user-defined pressure distributions. [13] formulated the continuous adjoint for inviscid and

laminar cavitating flows, based on the VoF method for tracking vapor generation. This was combined with the cut-cell technique to optimize hydrofoils, targeting max. lift and cavitation suppression. Finally, [14] developed a continuous adjoint method for an air-water system, without cavitation, and minimized the resistance of a ship hull. [14] included turbulence modeling, without developing its adjoint. Instead, leveraging the observation that the SDs of the objective function were mainly affected by near-wall effects, the authors differentiated the law-of-the-wall formula and, thus, derived an extra contribution in the diffusion term of the adjoint momentum equations. This modification was effectively applied in cases with objectives defined over the walls and provided better results than the frozen turbulence assumption.

Two-phase flow simulations are highly sensitive to turbulence, as demonstrated in [14], since phase interactions and steep velocity gradients increase turbulence production. Especially in cavitating flows, in which phase change occurs, turbulence effects are even more dominant, as reported in [15], which evaluated different turbulence models in a cavitating flow in a Venturi-type section. Keeping this in mind, turbulence model differentiation is expected to improve the SDs accuracy predicted by the adjoint. In single-phase flows, [2] was the first to include the differentiation of the turbulence model equations in the continuous adjoint, with a great improvement in the accuracy of SDs. Similarly to single-phase flows, this article develops the continuous adjoint system considering not only the cavitation model, but also the turbulence model equations.

The derivation of the continuous adjoint system introduces field integrals containing the derivatives of grid coordinates w.r.t. the design variables, commonly referred to as grid sensitivities (in the discrete adjoint formulation). Computing grid sensitivities over the fluid domain can be done using volumetric Free Form Deformation (FFD) methods. In this case, grid sensitivities are directly available. However, the integration of FFD volumetric tools into CAD models presents significant challenges, thereby limiting their applicability in many industrial contexts. Alternatively, surface parameterization, which is more compatible with CAD environments, can be used. Then, the computation of grid sensitivities becomes time consuming, as it requires solving the

grid displacement equations twice per design variable to apply second-order accurate Finite Differences (FDs) schemes. The integrals containing grid sensitivities can either contribute directly to the SDs expression or be neglected (which is, of course, not recommended, [16]). An alternative approach, outlined in [16] and known as the Enhanced Surface Integral (E-SI) adjoint, eliminates these field integrals while preserving accuracy, by formulating and solving the adjoint to a Grid Displacement Model (GDM); additional adjoint fields are computed, which contribute to the SDs, expressed only in the form of surface integrals. While the E-SI continuous adjoint has been successfully applied in single-phase flows with objectives defined over the domain boundaries [16, 17], it has not yet been used for two-phase flows or volume-defined objective functions. This article develops the E-SI continuous adjoint to a two-phase flow model and, among others, uses an objective function which quantifies the vapor volume in the entire domain.

The developed primal and adjoint flow solvers extend the in-house GPU-enabled software PUMA. The primal two-phase solver is validated against numerical and experimental data and the SDs computed by the adjoint method, with and without the frozen turbulence assumption, are verified against those obtained using FDs. Constrained ShpO is performed in three cases, dealing with an isolated hydrofoil, a hemispherical head body and a hydraulic poppet valve.

2 Two-Phase Numerical Model

2.1 Primal System of Equations

The two-phase system is modeled using the homogeneous approach in which the amount of liquid in each cell is quantified by the liquid volume fraction, α ($0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$). Each phase is assumed to have constant density and viscosity. The liquid-vapor mixture density ρ and molecular viscosity μ depend on the local value of α and are computed as

$$\rho = \alpha\rho_\ell + (1 - \alpha)\rho_v, \quad \mu = \alpha\mu_\ell + (1 - \alpha)\mu_v \quad (1)$$

where indices ℓ, v stand for liquid and vapor. The α field is computed by numerically solving the VoF equation

$$R^{\text{VoF}} = \frac{\partial(v_k \alpha)}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho_\ell} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $v_k, k = 1, 2, 3$, are the Cartesian velocity components and \dot{m} is the mass transfer rate, approximated by the Kunz model [5]

$$\dot{m} = \frac{C_{\text{dest}} \rho_v \alpha \min(0, p - p_{\text{vap}})}{1/2 \rho_\ell v_{\text{ref}}^2 t_{\text{ref}}} + \frac{C_{\text{prod}} \rho_v \alpha^2 (1 - \alpha)}{t_{\text{ref}}} \quad (3)$$

with C_{dest} and C_{prod} being the evaporation and condensation rate coefficients; also p and p_{vap} stand for the static and vaporization pressure, respectively, and t_{ref} is the reference time scale, which is equal to a characteristic length divided by the reference velocity v_{ref} . The MF equations, for the liquid-vapor mixture, read

$$R_n^{\text{MF}} = \frac{\partial f_{nk}^{\text{inv}}}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\partial f_{nk}^{\text{vis}}}{\partial x_k} - S_n^{\text{cav}} = 0, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad (4)$$

with $\mathbf{f}_k^{\text{inv/vis}}$ being the inviscid/viscous fluxes and \mathbf{S}^{cav} the cavitation source term

$$\mathbf{f}_k^{\text{inv}} = \begin{bmatrix} v_k \\ \rho v_1 v_k + p \delta_{1k} \\ \rho v_2 v_k + p \delta_{2k} \\ \rho v_3 v_k + p \delta_{3k} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{f}_k^{\text{vis}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \tau_{1k} \\ \tau_{2k} \\ \tau_{3k} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{S}^{\text{cav}} = \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_\ell} - \frac{1}{\rho_v}\right) \dot{m} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$\tau_{mk} = (\mu + \mu_t) \left(\frac{\partial v_m}{\partial x_k} + \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_m} \right)$ is the stress tensor; the turbulent viscosity μ_t is computed as $\mu_t = \rho \tilde{\nu} f_{v1}$, where the $\tilde{\nu}$ field is the solution to the Spalart-Allmaras (SA, [18]) turbulence model equation

$$R^{\text{SA}} = \frac{\partial(\rho v_k \tilde{\nu})}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\rho}{\sigma} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left[(\nu + \tilde{\nu}) \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \right] + c_{b2} \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \right\} - \rho \tilde{\nu} (\mathcal{P} - \mathcal{D}) = 0 \quad (6)$$

where $\nu = \mu/\rho$ is the mixture kinematic viscosity and \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{D} are the production and destruction terms; their expressions can be found in [18], along with all model constants. \mathcal{P} requires the distance Δ of any point from the closest wall; this is computed by solving the Hamilton-Jacobi equation [2].

The CFD grid update in each ShpO cycle requires a GDM which computes the displacements d_l of the internal nodes, according to the imposed boundary displacements d_l^w . The differentiable Laplacian model is used

$$R_l^{\text{GDM}} = \frac{\partial^2 d_l}{\partial x_k^2} = 0, \quad l = 1, 2, (, 3) \quad (7)$$

The boundary conditions of the primal equations are summarized in Table 1, in which \mathbf{n} is the unit normal vector to the boundary and all quantities indexed by “in” or “out” are known. In the applications considered in this article, the flow enters the domain entirely in liquid state ($\alpha = 1$).

Boundary	p	\mathbf{v}	α	$\tilde{\nu}$	\mathbf{d}
S_W	$\frac{\partial p}{\partial n} = 0$	$v_k = 0$	$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial n} = 0$	$\tilde{\nu} = 0$	$d_k = d_k^w$
S_{in}	$\frac{\partial p}{\partial n} = 0$	$v_k = v_k^{\text{in}}$	$\alpha = 1$	$\tilde{\nu} = \tilde{\nu}^{\text{in}}$	$d_k = 0$
S_{out}	$p = p^{\text{out}}$	$\frac{\partial v_k}{\partial n} = 0$	$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial n} = 0$	$\frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial n} = 0$	$d_k = 0$

Table 1: Boundary conditions for the primal equations, $k = 1, 2, (, 3)$ for 2D (or 3D) cases.

2.2 Continuous Adjoint Formulation

This article considers ShpO applications in which the hydrodynamic force, either lift or drag, the total volume of vapor and the volumetric flow-integrated total pressure drop, serve as objective or constraint functions. These are:

$$F_{\text{Force}} = \int_S f_{\text{Force}} dS = \int_{S_W} (pn_k - \tau_{mk}n_m)r_k dS \quad (8)$$

$$F_{\text{Cav}} = \int_{\Omega} f_{\text{Cav}} d\Omega = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (1 - \alpha)^2 d\Omega \quad (9)$$

$$F_{p_t} = \int_S f_{p_t} dS = - \int_{S_{\text{in}}} p_t v_k n_k dS - \int_{S_{\text{out}}} p_t v_k n_k dS \quad (10)$$

In general, notations $F_S = \int_S f_s dS$ and $F_\Omega = \int_\Omega f_\Omega d\Omega$ will be used in the ensuing development, denoting whether the objective function is a surface or a field integral. In all surface integrals, the unit normal vector \mathbf{n} points outside Ω . In eq. (8), f_{Force} is nonzero only along S_W , while \mathbf{r} is a unit vector, vertical or parallel to the freestream velocity, for lift or drag, respectively; depending on the application, F_{Force} will be specified as F_{Lift} or F_{Drag} . Eq. (10) involves the total pressure, $p_t = p + \frac{1}{2}\rho v_k^2$ and f_{p_t} is nonzero only along $S_{\text{in/out}}$.

The shape parameterization introduces a vector of design variables b_i , $i = 1, \dots, N$, representing, in this article, the coordinates of the control points of B-Splines curves. The derivation of the continuous adjoint equations involves total $\frac{\delta\Phi}{\delta b_i}$ and partial $\frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial b_i}$ derivatives, as well as derivatives in the form of $\frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial x_k} \right)$, where Φ is any quantity. These are treated using the following formulas [16],

$$\frac{\delta\Phi}{\delta b_i} = \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial b_i} + \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial x_l} \frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i}, \quad \frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial x_k} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta\Phi}{\delta b_i} \right) - \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} \right), \quad (11)$$

which bring grid sensitivities $\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i}$ on board. Following the adjoint approach described in [16], which coined the term *Enhanced Surface Integral* or *E-SI adjoint*, the expensive computation of grid sensitivities is avoided by solving the adjoint to the GDM. Despite [16] clarifies that the GDM used in the adjoint formulation is not necessarily the same used to update the CFD grid, this article adopts the exact same model, eq. (7), in both cases. Although included in the developed software, the Hamilton-Jacobi equation and its adjoint will herein be omitted for the sake of decreasing complexity. Thus, the objective or constraint function, $F_{\text{obj/cns}}$, is augmented with the field integrals of the adjoint fields, Ψ^α , Ψ , $\Psi^{\tilde{\nu}}$ and Ψ^d , multiplied by the corresponding primal residuals

$$F_{\text{aug}} = F_{\text{obj/cns}} + \int_\Omega \left(\Psi^\alpha R^{\text{VoF}} + \Psi_n R_n^{\text{MF}} + \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} R^{\text{SA}} + \Psi_l^d R_l^{\text{GDM}} \right) d\Omega. \quad (12)$$

The differentiation of eq. (12) w.r.t. b_i , followed by a lengthy mathematical development, see [16], [19] (for single-phase flows, though) expresses $\frac{\delta F_{\text{aug}}}{\delta b_i}$ in terms of field and surface integrals, including total derivatives of flow variables $\left(\frac{\delta p}{\delta b_i}, \frac{\delta v_k}{\delta b_i}, \frac{\delta \alpha}{\delta b_i}, \frac{\delta \tilde{\nu}}{\delta b_i} \right)$ as well as derivatives of geometric quantities $\left(\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} \right), \frac{\delta(n_k dS)}{\delta b_i} \right)$ w.r.t. b_i . Field

integrals are eliminated by setting the multipliers of the total derivatives of flow variables in these integrals to zero, at all points within Ω . This gives rise to the system of the adjoint equations, namely

$$R^{\Psi^\alpha} = -v_k \frac{\partial \Psi^\alpha}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\partial \Psi_{m+1}}{\partial x_k} \left[v_m v_k (\rho_\ell - \rho_v) - \frac{\tau_{mk}}{\mu + \mu_t} \left(\mu_\ell - \mu_v + \frac{\partial \mu_t}{\partial \alpha} \right) \right] \\ - \left[\Psi_1 \left(\frac{1}{\rho_\ell} - \frac{1}{\rho_v} \right) + \frac{\Psi^\alpha}{\rho_\ell} \right] \frac{\partial \dot{m}}{\partial \alpha} + T^{\text{VoF}} + \frac{\partial f_\Omega}{\partial \alpha} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$R^{\Psi_n} = -A_{mnk} \frac{\partial \Psi_m}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\partial \phi_{nk}^{\text{vis}}}{\partial x_k} - \left[\Psi_1 \left(\frac{1}{\rho_\ell} - \frac{1}{\rho_v} \right) + \frac{\Psi^\alpha}{\rho_\ell} \right] \frac{\partial \dot{m}}{\partial p} \delta_{1n} \\ - \alpha \frac{\partial \Psi^\alpha}{\partial x_k} \delta_{k+1,n} + T_n^{\text{MF}} = 0, \quad n = 1, 2, 3(, 4) \quad (14)$$

$$R^{\Psi^{\tilde{v}}} = -\rho v_k \frac{\partial \Psi^{\tilde{v}}}{\partial x_k} - \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left\{ [\nu + (1 + c_{b2})] \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} (\rho \Psi^{\tilde{v}}) \right\} + \frac{c_{b2}}{\sigma} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_k^2} (\rho \Psi^{\tilde{v}} \tilde{v}) \\ + \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{\partial (\rho \Psi^{\tilde{v}})}{\partial x_k} (1 + c_{b2}) \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x_k} + \frac{c_{b2}}{\sigma} \rho \Psi^{\tilde{v}} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{v}}{\partial x_k^2} \\ - \rho \Psi^{\tilde{v}} \left(\mathcal{P} - \mathcal{D} + \tilde{v} \frac{\partial \mathcal{P}}{\partial \tilde{v}} - \tilde{v} \frac{\partial \mathcal{D}}{\partial \tilde{v}} \right) + \frac{\tau_{km}}{\mu + \mu_t} \frac{\partial \Psi_{m+1}}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial \mu_t}{\partial \tilde{v}} = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$R^{\Psi_l^d} = \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_l^d}{\partial x_k^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\Psi_1 \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_l} + \Psi_{m+1} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} (\rho v_m v_k + p \delta_{mk}) + \tau_{mk}^a \frac{\partial v_m}{\partial x_l} - \Psi_{m+1} \frac{\partial \tau_{mk}}{\partial x_l} \right) \\ + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\Psi^\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} (v_k \alpha) \right) + T_l^{\text{GDM}} - \frac{\partial f_\Omega}{\partial x_l}, \quad l = 1, 2(, 3). \quad (16)$$

These stand for the adjoint VoF (eliminating the field integral including $\frac{\delta \alpha}{\delta b_i}$), adjoint MF (for $\frac{\delta p}{\delta b_i}$, $\frac{\delta v_k}{\delta b_i}$), adjoint SA (for $\frac{\delta \tilde{v}}{\delta b_i}$) and the adjoint GDM (for $\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i}$) equations. In eq. (14) A_{nmk} is the Jacobian of the inviscid fluxes. Also, $\phi_k^{\text{vis}} = \left[0 \quad \tau_{1k}^a \quad \tau_{2k}^a \quad \tau_{3k}^a \right]^T$ are the adjoint viscous fluxes and $\tau_{mk}^a = (\mu + \mu_t) \left(\frac{\partial \Psi_{m+1}}{\partial x_k} + \frac{\partial \Psi_{k+1}}{\partial x_m} \right)$ the adjoint stresses.

Unlike previous articles on the adjoint method for two-phase flows [12–14], one may see the contributions T^{VoF} , T_n^{MF} and T_l^{GDM} to the adjoint VoF, MF, and GDM equations, respectively, which arise from the differentiation of the SA model equation. Contributions T_n^{MF} and T_l^{GDM} are known from the adjoint to single-phase flows, while the new contribution T^{VoF} arises from the SA model terms that depend on the mixture

ρ and μ . The aforementioned three contributions are

$$T^{\text{VoF}} = -\frac{\partial \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}}}{\partial x_k} \left[\tilde{\nu} v_k (\rho_\ell - \rho_v) - \frac{\rho}{\sigma} \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \alpha} \right] - \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \frac{\rho_\ell - \rho_v}{\sigma} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left((\nu + \tilde{\nu}) \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \right) + c_{b2} \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \right\} - \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\nu} \left\{ (\rho_\ell - \rho_v) (\mathcal{P} - \mathcal{D}) - \rho \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial \alpha} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \nu} (\mathcal{P} - \mathcal{D}) \right] \right\} \quad (17)$$

$$T_n^{\text{MF}} = -\rho \tilde{\nu} \frac{\partial \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}}}{\partial x_k} \delta_{k+1,n} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left[\rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\nu} \frac{\partial (\mathcal{P} - \mathcal{D})}{\partial \zeta} \frac{1}{\zeta} \varepsilon_{pkm} \varepsilon_{pqr} \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial x_q} \right] \delta_{m+1,n} \quad (18)$$

$$T_l^{\text{GDM}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \frac{\partial (\rho \tilde{\nu} v_k)}{\partial x_l} - \frac{1}{\sigma} \rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left\{ [\nu + (1 + c_{b2}) \tilde{\nu}] \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \right\} + \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{\partial (\rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}})}{\partial x_k} [\nu + (1 + c_{b2}) \tilde{\nu}] \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_l} - \frac{c_{b2}}{\sigma} \left[\frac{\partial (\rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\nu})}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_l} - \rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\nu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \right) \right] + \rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\nu} \frac{\partial (\mathcal{P} - \mathcal{D})}{\partial \zeta} \frac{1}{\zeta} \varepsilon_{pkm} \varepsilon_{pqr} \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial v_m}{\partial x_l} \right) \quad (19)$$

with $\zeta = \|\varepsilon_{pqr} \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial x_q}\|$ being the vorticity magnitude. The detailed mathematical development of the adjoint system, eqs. (13) to (16) can be found (for single-phase flows) in [16, 19]. Here, only the differentiation of the field integral containing the residual of the VoF equation, eq. (2), is demonstrated. Starting from

$$\int_{\Omega} \Psi^{\alpha} \frac{\delta R^{\text{VoF}}}{\delta b_i} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \Psi^{\alpha} \frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\partial (v_k \alpha)}{\partial x_k} \right) d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \Psi^{\alpha} \frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{\rho_\ell} \right) d\Omega \quad (20)$$

the first field integral on the right-hand-side (r.h.s.) is expanded as

$$\int_{\Omega} \Psi^{\alpha} \frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\partial (v_k \alpha)}{\partial x_k} \right) d\Omega = \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \Psi^{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta (v_k \alpha)}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega}_{\mathcal{T}_1} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega} \Psi^{\alpha} \frac{\partial (v_k \alpha)}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega}_{\mathcal{T}_2}. \quad (21)$$

By applying the Green-Gauss theorem, term \mathcal{T}_1 becomes

$$\mathcal{T}_1 = \underbrace{\int_S \Psi^{\alpha} n_k \frac{\delta (v_k \alpha)}{\delta b_i} dS}_{\mathcal{T}_{\text{BC}}} - \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \Psi^{\alpha}}{\partial x_k} v_k \frac{\delta \alpha}{\delta b_i} d\Omega - \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \Psi^{\alpha}}{\partial x_k} \alpha \frac{\delta v_k}{\delta b_i} d\Omega \quad (22)$$

where \mathcal{T}_{BC} determines the adjoint boundary conditions while the multipliers of $\frac{\delta \alpha}{\delta b_i}$ and $\frac{\delta v_k}{\delta b_i}$ in the field integrals are included in eqs. (13) and (14), respectively. To avoid the computation of grid sensitivities in the whole domain, term \mathcal{T}_2 in eq. (21), using

the Green-Gauss theorem, becomes

$$\mathcal{T}_2 = \int_S \Psi^\alpha \frac{\partial(v_k \alpha)}{\partial x_l} n_k \frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} dS - \int_\Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\Psi^\alpha \frac{\partial(v_k \alpha)}{\partial x_l} \right) \frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} d\Omega. \quad (23)$$

Since $\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} = \frac{\delta d_l}{\delta b_i}$, the multiplier of $\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i}$ in the last integral contributes a term to the adjoint GDM equation, eq. (16), and, thus, the computation of this field integral is avoided. The first integral in eq. (23), written in terms of $\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i}$ at the boundary, contributes to the SDs, see below.

Additionally, the field integral containing the source term in eq. (20) is also expanded as

$$- \int_\Omega \Psi^\alpha \frac{\delta}{\delta b_i} \left(\frac{\dot{m}}{\rho_\ell} \right) d\Omega = - \int_\Omega \frac{\Psi^\alpha}{\rho_\ell} \frac{\partial \dot{m}}{\partial \alpha} \frac{\delta \alpha}{\delta b_i} d\Omega - \int_\Omega \frac{\Psi^\alpha}{\rho_\ell} \frac{\partial \dot{m}}{\partial p} \frac{\delta p}{\delta b_i} d\Omega \quad (24)$$

where the multipliers of $\frac{\delta \alpha}{\delta b_i}$ and $\frac{\delta p}{\delta b_i}$ in the first and second integrals on the r.h.s. give rise to source terms in eqs. (13) and (14), respectively. Similarly, the cavitation-related source term in the MF equations, eq. (4), yields two similar field integrals containing $\frac{\delta \alpha}{\delta b_i}$ and $\frac{\delta p}{\delta b_i}$, contributing to the same equations.

The differentiation of objective functions which are in the form of surface integrals, such as F_{Force} and F_{p_t} , contributes to the adjoint boundary conditions. On the other hand, the differentiation of F_{Cav} , the only volume-defined objective function in this article, w.r.t. b_i yields

$$\frac{\delta F_\Omega}{\delta b_i} = \frac{\delta F_{\text{Cav}}}{\delta b_i} = - \int_\Omega (1 - \alpha) \frac{\delta \alpha}{\delta b_i} d\Omega + \frac{1}{2} \int_\Omega (1 - \alpha)^2 \frac{\delta(d\Omega)}{\delta b_i} \quad (25)$$

where the first term contributes to eq. (13), as $\frac{\partial f_\Omega}{\partial \alpha}$. Since $\frac{\delta(d\Omega)}{\delta b_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left(\frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} \right) d\Omega$, [16], the last term in eq. (25) is rewritten as

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_\Omega (1 - \alpha)^2 \frac{\delta(d\Omega)}{\delta b_i} = \frac{1}{2} \int_S (1 - \alpha)^2 n_l \frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} dS - \frac{1}{2} \int_\Omega \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} (1 - \alpha)^2 \frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} d\Omega \quad (26)$$

where the last integral contributes the term denoted as $\frac{\partial f_\Omega}{\partial x_l}$ to eq. (16).

Overall, compared to the single-phase E-SI continuous adjoint presented in [16], the differentiation of the objective function F_{Cav} and the convection term in the VoF equation contributes additional terms to the adjoint GDM equations as well as the SDs.

Since the primal equations are coupled, the adjoint system inherits cross-contributions from the primal coupling terms. Differently from the primal problem, in which the VoF equation (eq. (2)) does not explicitly depend on $\tilde{\nu}$, the adjoint to the VoF equation (eq. (13)) includes contributions from the $\Psi^{\tilde{\nu}}$ field, embedded in the source term T^{VoF} , in eq. (13), due to the differentiation of the mixture ρ and μ in the SA model equation.

The adjoint boundary conditions are summarized in Table 2, where f_S stands for either f_{Force} or f_{p_t} , and \mathbf{t} refers to the unit tangent vector to the wall.

Boundary	Ψ	Ψ^α	$\Psi^{\tilde{\nu}}$	Ψ^d
S_W	$\frac{\partial \Psi_1}{\partial n} = 0, \Psi_{m+1} n_m = -\frac{\partial f_S}{\partial p},$ $\Psi_{m+1} t_m = \frac{\partial f_S}{\partial \tau_{kl} n_k t_l}$	$\frac{\partial \Psi^\alpha}{\partial n} = 0$	$\Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} = \frac{\sigma}{\nu + (1 + c_{b2})} \frac{\partial f_S}{\partial \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial n}}$	$\Psi_l^d = 0$
S_{in}	$\Psi_n n_k \frac{\partial f_{ak}}{\partial p} = -\frac{\partial f_S}{\partial p}$	$\frac{\partial \Psi^\alpha}{\partial n} = 0$	$\Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} = 0$	$\Psi_l^d = 0$
S_{out}	$\Psi_n n_k \frac{\partial f_{ak}}{\partial v_m} = -\frac{\partial f_S}{\partial v_m}$	$\Psi^\alpha = 0$	$\frac{\partial \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}}}{\partial n} = 0$	$\Psi_l^d = 0$

Table 2: Boundary conditions for the adjoint equations.

The remaining surface integrals contain derivatives of geometric quantities only, and contribute to the SDs, as

$$\frac{\delta F_{\text{aug}}}{\delta b_i} = \int_{S_W} W_1 \frac{\delta x_l}{\delta b_i} dS + \int_{S_W} W_2 \frac{\delta(n_k dS)}{\delta b_i} \quad (27)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} W_1 &= \frac{\partial f_S}{\partial x_l} - \Psi_1 \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_l} n_k - \Psi_{m+1} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} (\rho v_m v_k + p \delta_{mk}) n_k + \Psi_{m+1} \frac{\partial \tau_{km}}{\partial x_l} n_k \\ &\quad - \tau_{km}^a \frac{\partial v_m}{\partial x_l} n_k - \Psi^\alpha \frac{\partial(\alpha v_k)}{\partial x_l} n_k - \frac{\partial \Psi_l^d}{\partial x_k} n_k + f_\Omega n_l - \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \frac{\partial(\rho \tilde{\nu} v_k)}{\partial x_l} n_k \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\sigma} \rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left\{ [\nu + (1 + c_{b2}) \tilde{\nu}] \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \right\} n_k - \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{\partial(\rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}})}{\partial x_k} [\nu + (1 + c_{b2}) \tilde{\nu}] \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_l} n_k \\ &\quad + \frac{c_{b2}}{\sigma} \left[\frac{\partial(\rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\nu})}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_l} - \rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\nu} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\nu}}{\partial x_k} \right) \right] n_k - \rho \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \tilde{\nu} \frac{\partial(\mathcal{P} - \mathcal{D})}{\partial \zeta} \frac{1}{\zeta} \varepsilon^{pkm} \varepsilon_{pqr} \frac{\partial v_r}{\partial x_q} \frac{\partial v_m}{\partial x_l} n_k, \\ W_2 &= \frac{\partial f_S}{\partial(n_k dS)} + \Psi_1 v_k + \Psi_{m+1} \rho v_m v_k - \Psi_{m+1} \tau_{km} + \Psi^\alpha \alpha v_k + \Psi^{\tilde{\nu}} \rho \tilde{\nu} v_k \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \Psi_{k+1} \tau_{lp} n_p n_l - \Psi_{q+1} n_q \tau_{lp} n_p t_l t_k + \frac{1}{\sigma} \rho \Psi^{\bar{\nu}} [\nu + (1 + c_{b_2}) \bar{\nu}] \frac{\partial \bar{\nu}}{\partial x_k}. \quad (28)$$

2.3 Discretization and Numerical Solution

The in-house GPU-accelerated single-phase primal and adjoint solver PUMA was extended to two-phase cavitating flows by implementing the equations presented in sections 2.1 and 2.2.

The discretization of all equations is based on the vertex-centered finite-volume approach for unstructured/hybrid grids. The inviscid fluxes in the primal VoF (eq. (2)), MF (eq. (4)) and SA (eq. (6)) equations are discretized using a second-order Roe scheme [20] with the Van Leer slope limiter [21]. The adjoint convective fluxes in eq. (13) to (15) are discretized using a second-order non-conservative scheme [22]. PUMA employs mixed precision arithmetic [22], meaning that the Jacobian of the residuals, required for residual smoothing, is computed in double-, but stored in single-precision, minimizing GPU memory footprint and transactions (through vectorized write/loads) without affecting the solution accuracy.

The equations are preconditioned in pseudo-time, [23] and integrated using a multi-stage Runge–Kutta scheme. At each Runge–Kutta stage, a residual smoothing technique performs a user-defined number of linear solver iterations. The solution update in each stage starts from the coupled system of the MF, followed by the VoF and, finally, the SA equation. The same sequence is applied to both primal and adjoint systems. Since the differentiation of the GDM equations does not add contributions to the rest of the adjoint equations, the adjoint GDM equations (eq. (16)) are solved using the Quasi-Minimal Residual Variant of the Bi-CGSTAB (QMRCGSTAB) [24] linear solver, upon convergence of the adjoint MF, VoF and SA equations.

In each cycle of the ShpO loop, the parameterized domain boundaries are modified according to the current design variables and the internal grid is morphed by solving the GDM equations. Next, the primal equations are solved and the quantities of interest (objectives, constraints) are computed. The solution of the adjoint equations enables the computation of SDs, eq. (27), which are finally used to update the design

variables. This update is performed with the Sequential Least Squares Programming (SLSQP) algorithm [25], which uses low-cost approximations to the Hessian matrices.

3 Optimization Results

3.1 Hydrofoil

The first case starts with the assessment of the primal solver in the flow around an isolated NACA0012 hydrofoil, a well-established benchmark in the framework of cavitating flow simulations, followed by two optimization cases. The density ratio ρ_ℓ/ρ_v is set to 1000 and the Reynolds number based on the chord is $Re_c = 2 \times 10^6$, computed using the kinematic viscosity of liquid water. The farfield velocity and flow angle are $v_{\text{ref}} = 1.453 \text{ m/s}$ and $\alpha_{\text{ref}} = 1^\circ$ and the cavitation number is $\sigma = \frac{p_{\text{ref}} - p_{\text{vap}}}{1/2 \rho_\ell v_{\text{ref}}^2} = 0.42$, where p_{ref} is the farfield pressure. The phase change coefficients are set to $C_{\text{dest}} = 100$ and $C_{\text{prod}} = 30$; also $t_{\text{ref}} = \frac{c}{v_{\text{ref}}} \simeq 0.68 \text{ s}$. The first nodes off the solid wall have, on average, $y^+ \simeq 0.1$. The farfield boundary is about 30 chords away from the hydrofoil, and the grid consists of 10^5 nodes.

Fig. 1 (left) reveals the formation of a cavitation bubble on the suction side, extending from the leading edge to mid-chord, without reverse flow at the cavitation closure region, as also demonstrated in [26]. Fig. 1 (right) compares the wall pressure coefficient, $C_p = \frac{p - p_{\text{ref}}}{1/2 \rho_\ell v_{\text{ref}}^2}$, on the suction side with the numerical results of [26], showing a very good agreement. A pressure plateau is observed, at $C_p = -\sigma$ (or $p = p_{\text{vap}}$), at the first half of the suction side. The shape of the vapor cloud, delineated by the iso-line $\alpha = 0.99$, Fig. 1 (right), matches the data of [26]; the only minor difference is that the cavitation region predicted by the present code is slightly shorter, as also shown by the pressure recovery, (drop of $-C_p$ in Fig. 1 (right)), on the suction side.

Fig. 1: NACA0012 Hydrofoil: Computed α field (left), and comparison of the suction side C_p and $\alpha = 0.99$ iso-line against [26] (right).

To verify the accuracy of the continuous adjoint method in two-phase flows, the computed SDs of F_{Lift} and F_{Cav} are compared against FDs (considered as reference derivatives). Each side of the hydrofoil is parameterized using a Bézier curve, with P_i and S_i ($i = 1, \dots, 8$) being the control points of the pressure and suction side, respectively. The leading and trailing edge control points ($i = 1$ and $i = 8$, respectively) are fixed, while the remaining points are allowed to move only in the normal to the chord direction. Therefore, the vectors of design variables, denoted as b_i^P and b_i^S , stand for the y-coordinates of P_i and S_i with $i = 2, \dots, 7$. Fig. 2a and 2b show the SDs of these two quantities, computed by FDs and the adjoint. The latter has been used with and without the frozen turbulence assumption. When the adjoint turbulence model equation is solved, the SDs computed by the adjoint method are in good agreement with FDs, confirming the accuracy of the developed adjoint method. The derivatives associated with the control points at the first half of the suction side, where cavitation occurs, take on large value. The comparison between frozen turbulence adjoint and FDs, Fig. 2, shows that the strong influence of the turbulence model on cavitating flows leads to wrong SDs, both in magnitude and sign, if the adjoint turbulence model equation is not solved. The takeaway message is clear: similar to single-phase flows, it is strongly recommended to include the adjoint turbulence model equation(s) into the system of adjoint equations, for two-phase flows with cavitation, too.

Fig. 2: NACA0012 Hydrofoil: Comparison of SDs computed by the two-phase adjoint with and without the frozen turbulence, and FDs, for the two quantities of interest.

The sign of the SDs of the objective functions, Fig. 2, gives the direction in which the control points should be displaced to enhance the objective function. For instance, in Fig. 2a, the derivatives at b_2^P and b_2^S , which affect the region near the leading edge, exhibit opposite signs. This suggests that the control points should move toward each other, to decrease the hydrofoil thickness at the leading edge. Notably, the derivative at b_2^S takes on a large value, indicating that lift is strongly influenced by the geometry of the suction side region, where cavitation develops. The negative sign of this derivative implies a reduction in suction side concavity. Similarly, b_7^P and b_7^S influence the region near the trailing edge. Here, the derivatives have the same sign, suggesting that both control points should move in the same direction to locally increase the camber. Similar considerations can be made for the derivatives of F_{Cav} in Fig. 2b. In this case, however, the optimization intends to minimize this quantity. Thus, the control points should move in the opposite direction compared to that indicated by the derivatives.

Having verified the SDs, two optimization runs were carried out. The first one (run-L) aims at max. lift, F_{Lift} , while the second one (run-C) at min. cavitation, F_{Cav} , while the drag should keep its initial value in both cases. The optimized hydrofoils from run-L (opt-L), and run-C (opt-C), are illustrated in Fig. 3. Opt-L, Fig. 3 (left),

shows that the optimization displaces the control points to increase the hydrofoil camber and, thus, lift. However, a more cambered hydrofoil entails the formation of a larger vapor cloud, due to the greater pressure drop on the suction side. Therefore, in the opt-L case, the suction side changes from convex to concave, leading to a milder pressure drop that limits further vapor production, with a negative impact on lift. On the other hand, for the opt-C hydrofoil, Fig. 3 (right), cavitation on the suction side is suppressed. The opt-C shape resembles the characteristics of a supercritical airfoil, with a nearly flat suction side up to 75% of the chord. The flow around the opt-C geometry features lower acceleration and, thus, lower pressure drop.

Fig. 3: NACA0012 Hydrofoil: Liquid volume fraction field over the opt-L (left) and opt-C (right) hydrofoil.

Fig. 4 shows the convergence of the lift coefficient (C_L), left, and F_{Cav} , right, and the history of the drag coefficient (C_D) in each optimization. In both cases, the optimizer improved the objective function while retaining C_D . These results underline the association of cavitation and hydrodynamic force. The opt-L shape significantly rises the hydrofoil C_L , at the expenses of a greater vapor production, ($F_{Cav} = 2.72 \times 10^{-3}$ for the opt-L hydrofoil compared to $F_{Cav} = 7.24 \times 10^{-4}$ for the reference geometry). On the other hand, the opt-C shape suppresses cavitation by restricting pressure drop along the suction side; this, however, lowers C_L (down to 0.304 for the opt-C hydrofoil, from 0.492 of the reference geometry). In both cases, the discrepancy between reference and optimized C_D remains below 1% ($C_D = 0.605$ for the opt-L and 0.615 for the opt-C hydrofoils, compared to 0.609 of the reference geometry).

Fig. 4: NACA0012 Hydrofoil: Objective and constraint function history for the two optimizations, run-L (left) and run-C (right). F_{Lift} and F_{Drag} are presented in non-dimensional form (lift and drag coefficients; both with fixed denominators).

3.2 Hemispherical head body

The second case involves the turbulent cavitating flow around a 3D body with a hemispherical head followed by a cylindrical segment. The flow conditions are those of the experimental investigations of [27], which collects pressure distributions on differently shaped cavitating bodies used in several naval applications such as submarines, ships or torpedoes. The farfield velocity, $v_{ref} = 0.144 \text{ m/s}$, is aligned with the axis of symmetry. Two cavitation conditions, with $\sigma = 0.6$ and $\sigma = 0.4$, are studied. The Reynolds number, based on the hemispherical head diameter D , is $Re_D = 2 \times 10^5$. The mass transfer coefficients are set to $C_{dest} = 500$ and $C_{prod} = 50$. A C-type grid with about 7×10^5 nodes (handled as unstructured, though) is used; the average y^+ of the first nodes off the solid wall is $y^+ \simeq 0.4$.

The results of the numerical simulations, in the form of circumferentially-averaged C_p , as a function of the generatrix arc-length s , normalized by D , are shown in Fig. 5. In both cases, the agreement between numerical and experimental results of [27] is very satisfactory. As also observed in the hydrofoil case, cavitation leads to a region of constant pressure, equal to the vaporization one. For $\sigma = 0.6$, this plateau extends from $s/D \simeq 0.6$ to $s/D \simeq 1$, followed by a fast pressure recovery. For $\sigma = 0.4$, the

more intense cavitation causes the pressure plateaux to extend from $s/D \simeq 0.55$ to $s/D \simeq 1.3$, while the pressure recovery is slower than in the $\sigma = 0.6$ case.

Fig. 5: Hemispherical head body: Comparison of the circumferentially-averaged C_p computed by the present code (PUMA) and the experimental results of [27], for the reference geometry.

Fig. 6 illustrates the C_p distribution on the wall along with the $\alpha = 0.9$ iso-surface. At $\sigma = 0.6$, the pressure drop forms a vapor cloud close to the end of the hemispherical head and the first part of the cylindrical segment, while at $\sigma = 0.4$, evaporation increases, since a larger part of the surface features a low pressure causing phase change.

The optimization targets minimum cavitation by modifying only the head's shape. To preserve its axisymmetry, the head generatrix is parameterized with a Bézier curve, the control points of which are allowed to move only in the radial direction, thus retaining the length of the head component. The drag is also constrained and must not exceed the value of the reference geometry. It is noted that the drag is computed only on the head and the cylindrical segment up to one diameter in length, because the performance metrics are associated with the flow in the front part of the body.

Fig. 6 shows that cavitation is significantly reduced, as depicted by the smaller size of the $\alpha = 0.9$ iso-surface. In particular, for $\sigma = 0.6$, Fig. 6a, F_{Cav} dropped by 21% w.r.t. the initial value, while for $\sigma = 0.4$, Fig. 6b, by 25%.

Fig. 6: Hemispherical head body: Comparison of the $\alpha = 0.9$ iso-surface (in light gray color), along with the colormap of C_p over the solid wall, for the two σ values, between the reference and optimized geometries.

Fig. 7 compares the optimized and reference geometry in terms of the radial wall displacement $\Delta r = r_{\text{opt}} - r_{\text{ref}}$, where $r_{\text{opt/ref}}$ refers to the optimized and reference radius of a wall node, respectively. The colormap of Δr shows considerable differences between the two geometries. In the $\sigma = 0.6$ case, Fig. 7a, first the shape changes from convex to concave, allowing a smoother pressure drop which delays the onset of cavitation. Further downstream, the body radius increases compared to the reference geometry, producing a small bump at the junction of the head and the cylindrical segment. The pressure drop, followed by a rapid pressure recovery after the bump, results in a small cavitation area. In the $\sigma = 0.4$ case, Fig. 7b, the optimized geometry features

larger differences from the reference one. The head shape modifications resemble those observed in the $\sigma = 0.6$ case, with higher Δr magnitude though. The convex-concave change delays the formation of the vapor cloud, as also shown in Fig. 6. However, unlike the $\sigma = 0.6$ case, no bump is formed at the head/cylindrical segment junction.

Fig. 7: Hemispherical head body: Comparison between the optimized and reference radial displacement of the solid wall for the two σ values.

The aforementioned observations also reflect on the wall pressure distribution. Fig. 8 compares the circumferentially-averaged C_p of the reference and the optimized geometries for $\sigma = 0.6$, Fig. 8a, and $\sigma = 0.4$, Fig. 8b. In the former case, at $s/D \simeq 0.57$ of the reference geometry, the pressure drops below p_{vap} , and C_p becomes practically equal to $-\sigma = -0.6$, leading to cavitation. The vapor extends approximately to the end of the head $s/D \simeq 0.78$. At the closure of the vapor cloud, the strong adverse pressure gradient results in a reverse flow region that extends up to $s/D \simeq 1.1$, as shown by the streamlines in Fig. 8a. In the optimized case, the pressure exceeds p_{vap} for $s/D \lesssim 0.7$, due to a change in the surface curvature. At $s/D \simeq 0.7$, a bump causes the pressure to drop below p_{vap} , signifying the onset of cavitation. The fast pressure recovery after the bump restricts the cavitation size, while the reverse flow is substantially reduced due to the smaller and more compact vapor cloud. For $\sigma = 0.4$, Fig. 8b, the larger radial difference between the reference and optimized geometries

strongly affects the wall pressure distribution. At $s/D \simeq 0.4$, a bump, denoted by the red area in Fig. 7b, followed by a concave surface, blue area, reduces the pressure drop, hindering the evaporation. The pressure drops below p_{vap} at $s/D \simeq 0.78$, where the head connects to the cylindrical segment. In this case, the lower vapor volume produces a shorter recirculation bubble at the closure region of the vapor cloud, as can be seen by examining the streamlines in Fig. 8b.

Fig. 8: Hemispherical head body: Comparison of the circumferentially-averaged C_p and the streamlines at the closure region of the vapor cloud, for the reference and optimized geometries. Cavitation is identified by the $\alpha = 0.9$ contour (indicated by the gray surface).

To better analyze the interaction of the vapor cloud and the recirculation regions, Figure 9 shows the $\alpha = 0.9$ iso-line along with the circumferential component of the vorticity field on the meridional plane; the streamlines are used to indicate the recirculation bubbles. For both $\sigma = 0.6$ and 0.4 , Figure 9 reveals the presence of a shear layer with increased vorticity developing around the liquid-vapor interface. The shear layer separates from the vapor cloud and encompasses a recirculation bubble that interacts with the closure region of the cavity. As the optimization reduces the amount of vapor, vorticity production results in a thinner shear layer forming a more compact recirculation bubble with higher vorticity, compared to the reference flow

fields. In both cases, the stronger recirculation stretches the tail of the vapor cloud in the streamwise direction.

Fig. 9: Hemispherical head body: The $\alpha = 0.9$ iso-line (thick black curve), colormap of circumferential component of the vorticity field ω and streamlines, for the two σ values. Comparison between the reference and optimized geometries.

3.3 Hydraulic poppet valve

The last case is concerned with the ShpO of a hydraulic poppet valve. These valves are commonly used for pressure relief, directional flow control, and flow rate regulation. However, at certain valve positions, the pressure drop, caused by the flow acceleration in the restriction between the valve seat and the poppet surface, Fig. 10, causes the onset of cavitation. Therefore, this optimization aims to minimize the vapor generation in this area while retaining the total pressure drop between inlet and outlet, as these valves are mainly used to control the flow pressure in hydraulic circuits.

The working fluid is hydraulic oil, with density $\rho_\ell = 850 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and dynamic viscosity $\mu_\ell = 0.046 \text{ Pa} \cdot \text{s}$. The geometry and flow conditions are those of the experimental study, [28], with an inlet velocity $v_{\text{in}} = 7.8 \text{ m/s}$ and an outlet static pressure

Fig. 10: Hydraulic poppet valve: Computational domain. The valve seat and poppet correspond to the top and bottom boundaries of the restriction, respectively. The green curve indicates the part of the valve seat wall that has been parameterized and modified during the optimization loop.

$p^{\text{out}} = 1.4 \text{ MPa}$. The vaporization pressure is set to $p_{\text{vap}} = 20 \text{ kPa}$, which is a typical value for hydraulic oil at the operating conditions described in the experiment report; the density ratio is $\rho_\ell/\rho_v = 1000$. The simulation is performed on a 2D section of the geometry and the computational domain is sketched in Fig. 10, where $s = 0.65 \text{ mm}$ and $s/h = 1.15$. Since the domain is symmetric, half of it is simulated. The channel outlet section has been extended to eight times the inlet height, to ensure flow recovery after the restriction and subsequent expansion. A structured grid with approximately 5×10^4 nodes is used; the first nodes off the solid walls have, on average, $y^+ \simeq 0.1$. The results of the numerical simulations in the reference geometry are presented in Fig. 11, left, which shows the liquid volume fraction field in the restriction, where flow acceleration and the associated pressure drop create a stretched and intense vapor cloud attached to the valve seat. This cloud is convected downstream in parallel to the restriction direction, due to high velocities developed in this region, without significant diffusion of the vapor phase. After the restriction, the rapid pressure recovery causes the vapor phase to condensate quickly. The pressure distribution on the seat, Fig. 12 left, where cavitation occurs, is compared with experimental measurements, with pressure probes distributed along the seat all around the chamfered edge and their position is reported in terms of the arc-length, d , with $d = 0$ corresponding to

the beginning of the seat. Here, the severe drop in static pressure causes the onset of cavitation.

The chamfered part of the valve seat is parameterized with a B-Spline curve to be used for the ShpO targeting cavitation reduction in the restriction. During the optimization, to ensure that the parameterized seat geometry connects and remains tangent to the walls, right before and after the chamfer, the first and last two control points coordinates were fixed. Furthermore, to retain the operating conditions of the poppet valve, F_{p_t} should keep its initial value. The optimization result is presented in Fig. 11, right. Note that, during the optimization, the total arc-length of the parameterized wall, d^{\max} , is free to change; however, in the present case, the final difference is negligible ($d_{\text{ref}}^{\max} = 1.0267 \text{ mm}$ compared to $d_{\text{opt}}^{\max} = 1.0264 \text{ mm}$). Cavitation is suppressed in the restriction of the optimized seat, as indicated by the α field.

Fig. 11: Hydraulic poppet valve: Computed α field in the reference (left) and optimized (right) geometries.

The comparison between the reference and optimized pressure distribution, Fig. 12 left, reveals that, in the optimized geometry, the pressure drop is substantially reduced, preventing the onset of cavitation. Note that, at $d \simeq 0.3 \text{ mm}$, the optimized shape features a localized reduction in static pressure compared to the reference curve which, however, is not sufficient to initiate evaporation. These observations are corroborated by the comparison of the reference and optimized seat shapes, Fig. 12 right, in which the origin of the x-y reference system is located at the beginning of the seat (i.e. of

the parameterized curve). In the part of the wall with $0.1 \text{ mm} \lesssim x \lesssim 0.3 \text{ mm}$, the optimization deformed the seat geometry to increase the gap between the seat and the poppet. Consequently, at the beginning of the restriction, the pressure drop is reduced since the flow accelerates less. However, to meet the total pressure drop constraint, the restriction becomes narrower further downstream, without though decreasing the pressure below p_{vap} .

Fig. 12: Hydraulic poppet valve: Comparison of the pressure distribution on the reference seat against experimental data of Oshima & Ichikawa [28] and that of the optimized geometry (left). Close-up view of the parameterized section of the valve seat for the reference and optimized geometries (right).

4 Conclusions

A GPU-accelerated primal and adjoint solver has been extended to two-phase turbulent cavitating flows. The primal solver was assessed in cases with experimental and numerical data and accurately captured the vapor cloud shape and the pressure distribution induced by cavitation, in both internal and external flows. For the first time, the continuous adjoint system to the two-phase cavitating flow equations has been derived according to the computationally-efficient E-SI continuous adjoint approach, which solves the extra system of the adjoint to the GDM equations to avoid the expensive computation of grid sensitivities in the entire domain. The comparison of

SDs between adjoint and FDs verified the accuracy of the adjoint solver. The differentiation of the SA turbulence model proved to be essential, since it provided higher SDs accuracy, compared to the frozen turbulence assumption, especially for objective functions defined in the whole domain, such as, the one quantifying cavitation. To assess the robustness of the developed software in ShpO applications, three cases were examined, including different objectives and constraints. In the isolated hydrofoil case, the optimizations separately increased the lift and practically suppressed cavitation, under constant drag. In the hemispherical body case, the optimizations for two different σ values yielded a considerably lower amount of vapor, whereas the length of the recirculation bubble at the cavity-closure regions was considerably decreased. Additionally, the drag of the optimized bodies remained below that of the reference geometry. In the hydraulic poppet valve, the valve seat was successfully reshaped to nearly eliminate cavitation in the narrow gap between the seat and the poppet, without compromising its performance in terms of pressure drop, a constraint imposed throughout the optimization process.

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Author Contributions

The first two authors developed and applied the presented method and produced the manuscript. The last three authors supervised the work and revised the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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